

POLITICAL SCIENCES

SIGNIFICANCE AND INFLUENCE OF JORGE ABELARDO RAMOS IN THE LATIN AMERICAN NATIONAL LEFT

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on an exhaustive analysis of the intellectual and political figure of Jorge Abelardo Ramos, with particular attention to his conception of the Latin American National Left. Through a rigorous qualitative examination of his work and career, we seek to characterize his vision of the region and evaluate his influence on the national movements of Latin America. The preliminary results indicate that Ramos developed an original interpretation of the historical development of Latin America, emphasizing the relevance of endogenous factors in the construction of nations and in the struggles for national emancipation. Therefore, it is a necessary rereading to understand, for example, the roots of contemporary Mexico. His thought, characterized by a marked nationalism and a critical stance towards imperialism, positioned him as a prominent figure in the Latin American left of his time. Through the analysis of his work, we aim to rescue those elements that retain their relevance to reflect on the contemporary challenges of the region: citizenship, democracy and to strengthen the integration processes. In conclusion, it is hoped that this work will contribute significantly to the enrichment of the academic debate on Latin American political thought, providing new perspectives and empirical evidence.

Keywords: Latin America, national movements, nation, politics.

Introduction.

"...The history of the Argentines unfolds on a territory that once embraced half of South America.

Where do our current borders come from? Is the origin of these borders perhaps due to a legitimate historical reason? Is there a language barrier, a certain obvious racial wall, that separates us? Or is it, on the contrary, the result of a political misfortune, a vicissitude of arms, a national defeat? Without a doubt, it appears as the result of a Latin American crisis, since Latin America was once very far away our great homeland. "We are a country because we could not integrate a Nation and we were Argentines because we failed to be Latin Americans." (Ramos j. A. 1969 pp.16-.17)

In this work we will address Jorge Abelardo Ramos' ideas on the Latin American National Left, characterizing his conception of this region, its significance and influence until the Mexican Revolution, with the bibliography suggested in the lecture. As an editor and disseminator, he was a reference in the defense of critical support for the national movements of Latin America. Through his writings and actions, he polemized with the positions of the traditional left and elite nationalism, which he placed as two sides of the same coin at the service of oligarchic interests.

The work gives us a valuable historical perspective on the dialectic between Regional Integration and secessionist tendencies, which have marked the future of our Nation. *"... The thorough research that Ramos carried out on our common history is combined with his uninterrupted political militancy, in order to strengthen the great Nation that San Martín and Bolívar dreamed of. It is, therefore, a scientific and militant book, which honors Jauretche's premise that, more than a history of*

politics, there is a politics of history..." (Ramos j. A. 1969 p.16)

Through it we explore the complex reality of Latin America, questioning whether we are a mosaic of independent nations or a single fragmented entity, seeking the roots of our identity in history. In addition, we review the concept of nation and ask ourselves: ¿Is it a social construct or an objective reality? And is it applicable to the Latin American reality?

Investigation.

One of the terms that we recreate from this work is that of Nation in order to understand its conception of Latin America. In this regard, Ramos adds: *"...Latin America lost the possibility of uniting in a Nation and advancing towards social progress, as the recently united States did in the north of the American continent. The North Americans fought a cruel civil war to abolish slavery. Thus they united their country against the slave separatism of the agricultural south, supported by the English. In an opposite direction, the agro-commercial oligarchies of the ports imposed themselves in Latin America over the unifying aspirations of Bolívar, San Martín, Artigas, Alamán, Morazán. The revolutionary generation of independence perished in village quarrels. It was the occasion that the skilled English and North American diplomats, the Poinsetts or the Ponsonbys, took advantage of to ally themselves with the commercial bourgeoisie and the Creole landowners, "the hacienda and the store." And they rewarded the hungry soldiers of Ayacucho with a sepulchral silence. These Creole soldiers had expelled from Latin America an Empire that held its colonies together, only to see other more powerful ones inserted in them, which helped their independence on condition that they remained disunited. They would be solitary republics with formal sovereignty, and open economies..." (Ramos, J. A. 1969 p.21)*

Jorge Abelardo Ramos 2020

The author, through this passage, raises a central idea about the historical development of Latin America in comparison to the United States. While the region lost a unique opportunity for unification, unlike the United States, which managed to consolidate itself as a nation through a civil war, Latin America was fragmented into various republics. On the other hand, local oligarchies prevailed over unifying ideals; independence leaders such as Bolívar, San Martín and others, who sought a continental union, were overtaken by local elites who prioritized their particular interests. However, foreign intervention was decisive: England and the United States, through their diplomats, took advantage of the internal divisions of Latin America to consolidate their influence and keep the region fragmented. Thus, the consequences of disunity were profound: The new Latin American republics, instead of advancing towards joint social progress, became dependent and politically unstable economies.

We can establish a relationship between Nation and Homeland: The nation provides the substrate on which patriotism develops, and the latter, in turn, reinforces the bonds of solidarity and social cohesion that characterizes a political community. The relationship between both concepts is complex and multifaceted, and has been the subject of numerous studies in the social sciences. It is important to highlight that both the nation and patriotism are dynamic and changing social constructions, subject to historical and political processes. Collective memory, although selective, is an essential element in the construction of a national narrative that legitimizes political power and unites society. (Pérez Gamón, C. M. 2024 p. 58)

As we delve deeper into the story, we see that the history of Brazil is a paradox. While the rest of Latin America abolished slavery after its independence, Brazil, despite its revolutions and political changes, maintained this practice for decades. This anomaly is due to a network of factors, such as economic exploitation based on slave labor, British influence, and the persistence of colonial structures.

Likewise, the colonial legacy and the struggles for independence generated a fragmentation in Latin America that made it difficult to build a united nation. The diversity of experiences, such as those of Cuba (a Spanish colony until 1898) and Brazil, demonstrate this division. This historical fragmentation, beyond economic factors, has been a persistent obstacle to regional development, perpetuating inequalities and delaying the progress of the continent.

"...The Spanish-Creole nation, united by the king, actually created by the Spanish monarchy, became a political archipelago, a confused dust cloud of multiple islands, governed by the former officers of Bolívar or San Martín. The Bolivarian leaders had sunk into disappointment or had become corrupted in power; they allowed themselves to be pampered by exporters and landowners. They licked their lips at seizing, after the bloodshed, the small sovereignties, transformed into prosperous satrapies. That story is told here..." (Ramos j. A. 1969 p.22) The author argues that, following the euphoria of independence, Latin America experienced a period of great political instability and fragmentation. Revolutionary ideals were lost amid internal struggles for power and the consolidation of new economic elites. Former heroes became local leaders, and new nations were plunged into a constant struggle for control of territory and resources.

Ramos argues that the construction of national identity in Latin America has been marked by excessive individualism that has fragmented the countries of the region. By focusing on differences and the search for external models, men and women citizens of this region have lost sight of the richness and diversity of Latin American identities, as well as the possibility of building a more solid regional identity. The exercise of citizenship rights supposes the recognition of a certain community belonging through which the individual develops and determines himself (Pérez Gamón C. M.2023 p.799)

"...Since Europe took possession of Latin America after the collapse of the Spanish Empire, it not only controlled the railway system, bananas, coffee, cocoa,

oil or meat. It accomplished a much more dangerous feat: it influenced a large part of the Latin American intelligentsia and drew a thin veil between the tragic reality of its own country and its admired external models. Thus, even the village rebels, and even the doctrines of "liberation," bore the mark of the master on their necks. With the seal of the West, they were like erroneous navigation charts, prepared to lead travelers astray. Everything Latin American or Creole was despised or detested. Since the Enlightenment or even before, there was no lack of precedents for this. From Buffon or the Abbé De Paw, to the most youthful graduate of some Faculty of Sociology or History in the last parish, they disdained the immense barbaric land." (Ramos, J. A. 1969 p.23)

The author argues that European influence in Latin America after Spanish colonization transcended the economic and political, penetrating deeply into the cultural and intellectual sphere.

In addition, this work raises how external influence, especially from Europe and the United States, has artificially shaped Latin America, imposing economic, social and political models that do not correspond to its reality. This imposition has led to a distortion of history, economic dependence and an inability to develop critical thinking, with which Ramos argues that:

Economic dependence Latin America has been subject to the dictates of the market and economic policies imposed from abroad, which has prevented the development of its own industry and has perpetuated the dependence on raw materials.

The imposition of social and political models, concepts and social categories from Europe (such as the bourgeoisie, the proletariat and the petite bourgeoisie) have been mechanically applied to Latin American reality, without considering the historical and cultural particularities of the region. The distortion of history The history of Latin America has been rewritten from a Eurocentric perspective, which has led to a misrepresentation of facts and the disqualification of key historical figures.

The influence of foreign ideologies, both Marxism-Leninism and North American sociological empiricism, have been uncritically adopted by Latin American intellectuals, which has hindered a deep understanding of the problems of the region. ..." (Ramos, J. A. 1969 p.25)

The following paragraphs present a strong critique of Latin American studies, pointing out the strong influence of Western perspectives (European and North American) that have hindered an authentic and profound understanding of Latin American reality. The main ideas developed are:

Dominance of Western perspectives, both from right-wing and left-wing approaches, interpretations of Latin America have been strongly influenced by Western categories and concepts. This has led to a distorted view of Latin American reality, where local problems have been reduced to imported theoretical schemes. Distancing itself from reality, social science, instead of addressing the concrete problems of Latin America, has become locked in abstract theoretical debates and in the

mechanical application of imported methodologies. Imposition of Western categories, concepts such as "bourgeoisie", "proletariat", "democracy" and "economic development" have been applied to Latin American reality without considering its historical and cultural particularities. Lack of understanding of the national question Latin American studies have tended to ignore the specificity of national struggles and reduce conflicts to simple class conflicts or the reproduction of European political models. Falsification of history Latin American history has been rewritten from a Western perspective, distorting the role of historical figures and the meaning of events. By imposing interpretative schemes, political, social and religious conflicts in Latin America have been interpreted through Western lenses, without considering the particularities of the Latin American context. A key example that the author uses is the case of the Jesuits in South America. While in Europe the confrontation between enlightened despotism and the Society of Jesus had a specific meaning, in Latin America this conflict acquired a totally different meaning, since the Jesuits defended the indigenous people against the interests of the colonizers. (Ramos, J. A. 1969 p.26)

National Project and Historical Context

In the words of Ramos: "...When the revolution began, all the great leaders had the national project in their heads. Egaña in Chile, Bolívar in Gran Colombia, Artigas, Monteagudo, San Martín and Dean Funes in the United Provinces, Morazán in Central America. The initiators, moreover, were children of the century that witnessed the movement of nationalities. The difficulties, however, exceeded all that was foreseeable. The immense extension, the weak land or sea communications, the low level of development of the productive forces, the lack of an economic and political center capable of dragging all the others towards a centralizing focus conspired against the project. It seemed that the only solution was purely military and that only the sword could ensure national unity in the process of independence. The optimal political form, for many of them, like San Martín and Belgrano, destined to maintain the continuity of the union for a long period, was the monarchical regime. The obsession of all the leaders was the anarchy, chaos and ensuing servitude. The Rioplatense Belgrano suggests crowning a Peruvian Inca, to ensure the adhesion of the millions of Indians of the old viceroyalties to the new order of things. The project is rejected, not because of my particular "democratism" of many "heroes" but because of the repugnance of the white Creole minority towards the "CUÍCOS", as the Buenos Aires deputies call the representatives of Indians or mestizos of Upper Peru. The social content of this "contempt" was nourished by the interests of the ranchers of Spanish origin of the humid pampas of the Plata, to whom only foreign trade mattered, or of the landowning lawyers of Peru or Upper Peru, exploiters of the indigenous "pongos" ..." (Ramos, J. A. 1969 p.141)

These leaders were products of their time, marked by the rise of nationalism and liberal revolutions in Europe.

However, reality exceeded expectations. The vast territorial extension, the lack of infrastructure and social inequality became formidable obstacles to the consolidation of these new nations. Exploring different solutions to instability and fragmentation, many leaders believed that only military force could guarantee national unity. Furthermore, the search for a strong central figure led some to propose the establishment of a monarchy as a way of ensuring the stability and continuity of the new order.

The fragment also reveals the deep social divisions that marked independent Latin America. Belgrano's proposal to crown an Inca reveals the tension between Creoles and indigenous people. The term "cuícos," used disparagingly to refer to indigenous representatives, shows the contempt and racism rooted in colonial society. Behind this situation lay economic interests. The Creoles, mostly landowners and merchants, saw the indigenous people as a cheap and submissive labor force. As a consequence, the inability to overcome these social divisions and build an inclusive nation was one of the great failures of the independence projects.

We make a brief characterization of the Men who made history following the guiding thread of the work we are analyzing:

San Martín: a Creole, son of a Spanish captain, played a fundamental role in the independence processes of the Hispanic American nations. Influenced by the ideas of the Enlightenment and the Masonic lodges, he became a fervent defender of the independence cause. His objectives and actions: Hispanic American unity, San Martín was a fervent defender of the union of the former Spanish colonies into a single nation. His objective was to create a confederation of states that would guarantee the independence and progress of all of America; Crossing of the Andes and liberation of Chile, one of his greatest military feats was the crossing of the Andes, with which he managed to free Chile from Spanish rule; Proclamation of Argentine independence, under his influence, the United Provinces of the Río de la Plata declared their independence from Spain in 1816; Inca monarchy, San Martín proposed the idea of establishing a constitutional monarchy presided over by a descendant of the Incas, with the aim of unifying the Hispanic American nations and attracting the support of the indigenous populations; Coinciding with Bolívar, although their ideas on the form of government differed slightly (San Martín proposed a monarchy, while Bolívar a republic), both leaders shared the goal of achieving independence and unity in Latin America, "...Although San Martín suggested the establishment of a constitutional monarchy presided over by an Inca king to attract the sympathy of the indigenous masses of Upper and Lower Peru, while Bolívar aspired to a republic with a lifelong presidency, both Liberators cherished the same purpose, a "Nation of republics", closely united in the face of the dispersion of the immense geography and the disintegrating intrigues of foreign Empires..." (Ramos, J. A. 1969 p.142)

Simón Bolívar: The text describes the formation and revolutionary awakening of Simón Bolívar, framed in the historical context of the late 18th and early 19th centuries. Origin and training: Bolívar came from a

family of the Venezuelan Creole aristocracy, the "mantuanos". His teacher, Simón Rodríguez, an enlightened and radical intellectual, had a profound influence on his thinking. Rodríguez, who had witnessed the French Revolution, instilled in Bolívar ideas of liberty, equality and fraternity. Together they toured Europe, where Bolívar witnessed historic events such as the coronation of Napoleon and became involved in Masonic lodges. These experiences, together with Rodríguez's teachings, awakened in him a deep longing for freedom and a revolutionary spirit. Existential crisis and dissipation: Despite his initial commitment to revolutionary ideas, Bolívar went through a stage of dissipation and waste, which generated tensions with his mentor. The Oath of Monte Sacro After a period of disillusionment, Bolívar and Rodríguez met again and, in an act of profound symbolic significance, swore on Monte Sacro, near Rome, to free America from the Spanish yoke. This oath, loaded with references to Roman history and revolutionary ideals, marked a turning point in Bolívar's life. (Ramos, J. A. 1969 pp.142-143)

"...From the silly homeland to Great Colombia..." (Ramos, J. A. 1969 p.144) It is a recurring metaphor in Colombian historiography to represent the passage from an initial stage of instability and fragmentation to an ambitious project of continental unity. However, this dichotomy simplifies the complexity of the historical processes and can hide the multiple facets of both periods. Despite this, this phrase remains useful to analyze the causes of the fragmentation of Gran Colombia and to reflect on the challenges of national construction in Latin America.

"...The first Junta, headed in 1811 by Fulgencio Yegros, proposed the Confederation of Paraguay with the other provinces of America of the same origin and mainly with those that comprised the demarcation of the former Viceroyalty. All the revolutionary leaders, from one end to the other of the Latin American nation, will proclaim their status as "Americans", whether they are from Caracas, New Granada, Argentina, Upper Peru, the East or Chile. For all of them, the city or region of birth will be, for a whole period, "the small homeland." Of all of them, it was Bolívar who most categorically expressed the common national consciousness. In a speech to the Division of Urdaneta, Bolívar said in 1814: "For us, the homeland is America." Bolívar was convinced that independence had been premature, precipitated by the Napoleonic invasion. It was obvious that the independence of the American colonies, with their economic and social weakness, could and should fall prey to internal dissolution and economic dependence on some great world power, in this case, Great Britain..." (Ramos, J. A. 1969 pp.145-146)

After achieving independence, the new American nations faced a fundamental dilemma: ¿should they unite in a large confederation or go their separate ways? Initially, the tendency towards division prevailed. Each region sought its own autonomy, which led to a period of great instability and internal conflict. In contrast, Simón Bolívar was a fervent defender of Latin American unity. His vision was to build a great nation that would encompass the entire continent, thus avoiding weakness and dependence on foreign powers. The idea

of a united America was not exclusive to Bolívar; other independence figures, from the precursors to the first governments, shared this vision. The independence leaders promoted a strong American identity, above regional identities. However, the homeland remained important to many.

Ramos recreates Simon Bolívar's ideas on the independence of Latin America and his vision of the future of the new nations: Bolívar recognized the importance of economic development prior to independence, but historical circumstances forced him to act hastily. Despite his desire for a great unified nation, Bolívar was aware of the social and economic differences between the different regions of Latin America. The main points that we can highlight: premature independence; America was considered not ready for independence due to the lack of economic development and the absence of a strong central government; the Ideal of a great nation, despite the difficulties, Bolívar dreamed of a great unified nation in Latin America, Distrust in representative governments he was skeptical about representative governments due to the lack of a solid social base in Latin America, Need for centralized governments, even though his ideals were political Bolívar was aware of the importance of the economy to consolidate the independence and development of the new nations. Thus, Bolívar's ideas were limited by the historical and social circumstances of his time. His focus was on political independence and unification, but he did not address social inequalities in any depth. ...” (Ramos, J. A. 1969 pp.146-147)

“...But if Marx's critical thought can shed a penetrating light on the reality of Latin America, it will be on condition that it conceives it as a whole> in other words, it is necessary to bring Marx together with Bolívar. After the loss of Bolivarian power, Latin America was considered as “a people without history”. The institutions, economic regimes and political systems imposed by imperialism bore the simian stamp of the products that Europe destined for the eccentric world...” (Ramos, J. A. 1969 -2002 Bolivarismo y Marxismo)

In this passage, Ramos raises a central idea: to fully understand the reality of Latin America, it is necessary to merge the perspectives of Marx and Bolívar. He suggests that Marx's critical thought, despite its value, cannot by itself illuminate the historical and social complexity of the region. It is essential to incorporate the Bolivarian vision, which emphasizes Latin American unity and identity, to achieve a more complete interpretation.

The author argues that by losing Bolivarian power, Latin America was stripped of its own history and subjected to a vision imposed by imperialism. This vision, according to Ramos, fragments and subordinates the region, reducing it to a mere imitation of Europe. The political, economic and cultural systems imposed by colonial powers hide the rich diversity and struggles of Latin America. Therefore, to overcome this situation, it is necessary to rescue and revitalize the Bolivarian legacy, integrating it with the analytical tools of Marxism.

Analysis of the Haitian Revolution and its Implications in Latin America.

Ramos offers a comparative analysis of the Haitian Revolution and the independence processes in Latin America, with a particular focus on the abolition of slavery and its sociopolitical implications. Key aspects he highlights: the precursor to independence, the Haitian Revolution, being the first successful slave rebellion and achieving independence from a European colony, set a fundamental precedent for the independence movements in Latin America. In addition, the radical abolition of slavery in Haiti contrasts with the more gradual processes conditioned by economic interests in other parts of Latin America. Leadership and resistance: Leaders such as Toussaint Louverture, Dessalines and Petion demonstrated exceptional military and organizational capacity, inspiring other liberation movements. The Haitian Revolution significantly influenced the ideas of Simon Bolívar, especially in relation to the abolition of slavery. Despite the discourses on freedom and equality, Latin American elites maintained slave or semi-slave practices, revealing a profound contradiction between their ideals and their actions.

The text highlights the importance of the Haitian Revolution as a historical milestone, underlining its pioneering character and its influence on subsequent independence processes. When comparing Haiti with other Latin American contexts, the diversity of approaches to the abolition of slavery and the complex power dynamics that shaped these processes become evident. The figure of Petion is fundamental when analyzing the connections between Haiti and the independence struggles in Latin America, especially its support for Simon Bolívar. This link highlights the importance of transatlantic networks and solidarities between liberation movements. On the other hand, the text criticizes the hypocrisy of Latin American elites, who often appropriated the revolutionary discourse without assuming the structural changes necessary to guarantee equality and social justice. (Ramos, J. A. 1969 pp.152-156)

Later, Ramos analyses the failure of Simón Bolívar's unifying project in Latin America and its historical implications. He argues that Bolívar's inability to consolidate a political union between the newly independent states of Latin America was a turning point that led to the fragmentation of the continent. Despite his charisma and leadership, Bolívar was unable to overcome deep regional divisions and the particular interests of local elites. Bolívar's project for a great Latin American nation faced insurmountable obstacles, such as rivalries between local elites and their priority to guarantee their own economic interests. Meanwhile, the dissolution of the Bolivarian project gave way to the formation of small nations with weak economies and dependent on the world market. From 1880 onwards, Latin American countries were integrated into the global economic system as suppliers of raw materials, losing their autonomy and becoming subject to the dynamics of international capitalism. Leaders such as Rafael Núñez, Roca, Latorre, Díaz, Santa María, Alfaro, Guzmán Blanco and Ruy Barbosa consolidated the power of local elites and promoted development models based on the exploitation of natural resources and the adoption of positivist ideologies. (Ramos, J. A. 1969 pp.297-298)

The text presents a critical analysis of the deep socioeconomic inequalities in Mexico during the Porfiriato. Through an examination of the power structures and production relations, it is evident how an oligarchic and foreign-based development model exacerbated social disparities. The concentration of land, the exploitation of natural resources and social repression formed a system that benefited a privileged minority. The Mexican Revolution, as a response to this situation, was an armed conflict that sought to radically transform the sociopolitical order, with land and social justice as *central axes*. (Ramos, J. A. 1969 pp.317-323)

"...Perhaps, for this reason alone, the revolution had been worth it: it had offered them a face, an identity. —Look: it's me. —Look at yourself: it's you. —Look, it's us..." (Ramos, J. A. 1969 pp.322-323)

With this sentence the author conveys the idea that the revolution, beyond the political or social changes, had a profound impact on the identity and self-esteem of the people involved. It gave them a sense of belonging and mutual recognition that they did not have before. The revolution, in this sense, becomes a process of self-discovery and the construction of a new collective identity. "Look: it is me" each individual, by looking at themselves, no longer sees themselves as an isolated individual, but as part of a larger group. The revolution would have given them a voice and visibility that they did not have before. "Look at yourself: it is you": this sentence invites reflection and mutual recognition. Each member of the group can see in the others a part of themselves, a deep connection based on shared experience and "Look, we are": this sentence ends with a sense of unity and collective strength. The "we are" emphasizes that they are stronger together, that their identity is built from their belonging to a group.

First Findings

Preliminary results indicate that Ramos developed an original interpretation of the historical development of Latin America, highlighting the relevance of endogenous factors in the construction of nations and in the struggles for national emancipation. Therefore, it is a necessary rereading to understand, for example, the roots of contemporary Mexico. His thought, characterized by a marked nationalism and a critical stance towards imperialism, positioned him as a prominent figure in the Latin American left of his time. Through the analysis of his work, we aim to rescue those elements that retain their relevance to reflect on the contemporary challenges of the region: citizenship, democracy and to strengthen the integration processes.

Conclusions.

Jorge Abelardo Ramos ideas on the Latin American National Left offer us a critical and profound look at the construction of nations in our region. By analyzing political fragmentation, the influence of neocolonialism, and the relationship between nation and underdevelopment, Ramos invites us to reflect on the complexity of our history and the challenges we face in the search for a common identity.

The question of whether we are a mosaic of independent nations or a single fragmented entity is complex and does not admit a simple answer. Ramos shows

us that the construction of a nation is a historical and social process, marked by tensions between centripetal and centrifugal forces. While cultural and political differences are evident, there is also a deep historical and cultural connection that unites us as Latin Americans.

The Nation, according to Ramos, is a social construct, the result of a historical and political process. In Latin America, this process has been marked by the struggle for independence, foreign interventions and social inequalities. The search for a national identity has been hampered by political fragmentation and the influence of external models.

The Haitian Revolution and the Mexican Revolution are paradigmatic examples of the struggles for freedom and the processes of decolonization in Latin America. By comparing the Mexican situation with that of other Latin American countries, we can identify common patterns of dependent development and the power dynamics that were established in the region. Political fragmentation and cultural dependence have been fundamental obstacles to the development of Latin America. The construction of a common Latin American identity and the overcoming of social inequalities are challenges that remain in force today. The legacy of figures such as José de San Martín and Simón Bolívar reminds us of the importance of unity and the struggle for liberation.

Final reflection: The history of Latin America is a history of struggles and contradictions. Despite the progress made, the region still faces major challenges.

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